

The Unfinished Agenda of National Integration

Ms. Deepshikha Parashar

Assistant Professor, Political Science

The IIS University, Jaipur

Dr. Pankaj Gupta

Assistant Professor

Dept. of Political Science

Govt. Arts College, Chimanpura, Jaipur

E- Mail : drpankajgupta1979@gmail.com

Abstract

National Integration is the feeling of oneness among the citizens of the country and rising above all the parochial loyalties. India is a perfect example of unity in diversity. It is inhabited by many races, castes, religions, languages. It implies a sense of belonging, a feeling of togetherness and unity. The most serious problem faced by India at present is, how to create and maintain the sense of integrity among the people. National integration is under threat due to many factors like caste, regionalism, communalism, linguism, and politics of secession. This paper makes an attempt to understand the term national integration and takes into consideration about various disintegrative forces and try to give insight on the probable solutions to the problem.

Keywords: National Integration, India, Nation, Threat

Introduction

It has been rightly said “United we stand but divided we fall”. A nation which is not united falls like a house of cards. The first and foremost concept of integration can be defined as, “a process of becoming whole¹.” However with the increase in the area and diversity complexities of the integration process increases. The concept of national integration is quite comprehensive. It covers all dimensions- social, political, economic, cultural, legal, educational, psychological. National integration refers specifically to the problem of creating a sense of territorial integrity above all the narrow and parochial loyalties. India has always been seen by our historians as a unique example of unity in diversity.

Why is national integration still incomplete?

A vital unfinished business of national integration relates to the diversities – cultural, linguistic and traditional, which are the integral parts of Indian social fabric.

The Secluded North Eastern States-North-East India is also described as 'the northwestern borderland of Southeast Asia'² The Northeast, which comprises eight per cent of India's total area and just four percent of its total population, has understandably remained on the periphery of mainstream. The region has suffered from so much neglect and apathy that it seems difficult to catch up with the other parts of India. Despite fairly rich natural resources, Assam, the region's biggest state suffers from the underdevelopment syndrome of low and almost stagnant agricultural deficiency, low rate of capital formation and mounting unemployment. The general underdevelopment has provided necessary breeding ground for social unrest which in turn has translated into insurgency. Though economic activities have significantly bridged the north-south gap but the North-East still needs to be integrated with rest of the country. Perhaps the ways to go about assimilating them into national mainstream is by improving connectivity and developing infrastructure to spur economic development.

Naxal Violence : The Biggest Internal Security Threat - India's development paradigm pursued since Independence led to commercialisation of forest resources, reducing the traditional access to forest produce, destroying their natural environment and besides that the construction of large dams caused wide-scale displacement of the tribal. The governance vacuum was filled by left-wing extremists called Naxalites, who exploited the isolation of the tribal and injustices done by state officials and money lenders to strengthen their cadre. Their aim is to destroy the Indian State and replace it with a communist state following the Maoist ideology. There has been a range of violence which has had no direct consequence on the rights of people but invariably ended up harming masses by way of disruption in the elections, destruction of schools, trains and rail lines, etc. Naxalites are powerful and effective in some areas in India because of the unresolved contradictions and issues in our society. They are now recognized as the biggest internal security risk for the country. The history of movement so far, has been the history of conflicts and splits. However one cannot deny that its history is also one of the merger.³

The 'Red Corridor' and Maoist Violence -- Over the years, a vast territory has been carved out covering 92,000 sq km area, called "Red Corridor" by the media. It has grown dramatically in last two decades along the East coast right from Nepal to Tamil Nadu. In the early 1990s the number of districts affected by varying degrees of Maoist violence stood at just 15 in four states. Maoists are currently believed to be operating in around 200 districts (of a total of 604 districts in the country) in 17 states. The worst affected states are Jharkhand, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, and Orissa. The poverty and backwardness of people in these forest covered areas has provided a fertile ground for the growth of Naxal/Maoists who have been gaining strength at every neglect of these people on the part of the governments.

Non-Implementation of Uniform Civil Code (UCC) - The issue of UCC dates back to the colonial period when the British applied a common criminal code on all but allowed different religious communities the freedom to have their own religious laws for personal matters like marriage, divorce, inheritance, adoption and maintenance. While framing the Constitution these

personal laws were debated extensively and UCC was opposed on the ground that it would destroy the cultural identity of minorities. Thus, a compromise was reached – the UCC was placed under the Directive principles, but which the state shall endeavor to achieve. Hence, we have Article 44 of the Constitution which says: “The State shall endeavor to secure for the citizens a uniform civil code throughout the territory of India.” And there is Article 14 which ensures right to equality. The main problem to be addressed through UCC is gender justice and ending up with non discriminatory civil code that is need of an hour.

Problems of National Integration in India

Diversity of Constituents- India is a heterogeneous society. It is made of a number of diverse groups. The first potential threat to the Indian nation state lies in this plurality. The Indian society was and is divided in terms of religion, caste, language and ethnic origin. One of the more serious challenges that Indian national leaders in India face even now is how to integrate the interests of the divergent group. Each of them has its own distinctive aspirations, history, and way of life. Attempts to minimize confrontation between conflicting groups do not always succeed. As we have already seen, the adoption of an egalitarian model of society is one important strategy to contain the divisive tendencies. It is, of course, necessary that these divisions are not allowed to threaten the nation – state.

Regionalism and Cultural Identities- Regionalism is a “multi dimensional composite phenomena as well as built in process within nationalism.”⁴ Some of the social elements having their separate cultural identity want to preserve it even at a political level and for this purpose some of these segments want further reorganization of the states. This is quite evident in the formation of States on linguistic basis. It is also evident in demands by some regional identities such as the Gorkha for Gorkhaland, for example. Creation of Jharkhand State is the outcome of the demands by some tribes’ .Regionalism has come to dominate several states in the country. Slogans like ‘Punjab for Punjabis’, ‘Maharashtra for the son of the soil’. The growth of powerful regional parties in states like Andhra Pradesh, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Bihar and Assam are ominous signals

Casteism - The Indian social system is a caste based hierarchical systems. The caste system plays disintegrative as well as integrative role in politics.”They are in the sense vehicle for transcending political the technical political illiteracy, which would restrict popular political participation.”⁵ Caste system when plays a disintegrative role in politics, it poses a serious threat to national integration .It disturbs the peace and cohesion in the society and widens gulf between different segments of society. Caste is not disappearing, nor is’ Casteism’- the political use of caste – for what is emerging in India is a social and political system which institutionalize and transforms but does not abolish the caste system.⁶ All the same in the absence of an alternative

basis for people to come together, caste continues to play a decisive role in Indian national politics.

Linguism - India is a multi linguistic nation with several well developed languages. Multi linguism is therefore one of the primordial facts of the Indian Polity. This issue was associated with Indian polity since independence movement. After independence the problem accentuated and language become the powerful instrument of politics. Despite accepting Hindi as a official language of the Republic by the Constituent Assembly, the language issue has remain unsettled. The conflict emerged between Hindi and English on one hand and Hindi and regional languages on the other. However the issue was finally settled by the Official Language (Amendment) Act, 1967, and it was decided that English will continue to be the Associate language of the Union for all the non Hindi states till the time they themselves opt for Hindi.⁷ Although there have been few incidents of violence, strains and tension but after more than 60 years of independence our country is mature enough to resolve the issue in a democratic manner..

Communalism - Bipin Chandra views Communalism as an ideology which spreads a communal belief system.⁸ We may identify three broad categories of communalism in India.⁹ These are- assimilative communalism, secessionist communalism and welfarist communalism. This tendency runs counter to the notion of the secular nation – state that India purports to be. Secularism in the Indian context is defined as the peaceful co-existence of all religions without State patronage to any of them. Yet, in a secular State like India, we very often hear, see and read about communal conflicts. The communalism manifest in the form of fanaticism and religious orthodoxy and led to the feeling of hostility among various communities. The most well known clashes have been between Hindus and Muslims. Some cities such as Moradabad, Meerut, Aligarh and Baroda etc. has appeared as the centre of communal riots.

Regional Disparities - The unequal development of different regions of India since independence has negatively affected the character of national integration. The unequal development has become the major cause of many social movements after the independence. For instance, the Jharkhand movements which involved tribal groups from Bihar, M.P. Bengal and Orissa stresses the backwardness of the region among other issues. While demanding a separate State, people, involved in this movement argue that the rich natural resources of the area have been drained out to benefit others. Thus the regional disparities in terms of socioeconomic development have at times proved to be a threat to the concept of united nation-state.

Ethno nationality and Ethnic Conflicts - The main obstacle to the development of national integration is the existence of ethnic minorities within the state who resist integrative tendencies. There are the six major racial groups constituting the present population of India who immigrated into this country at different types of time.¹⁰ Ethno nationalism is a phenomenon of political movement launched on the basis of ethnic identity. Although nationhood is denied to the Nagas, the Nagas understand themselves as nation in the sense of ethno nationality It is to

mention that the nation-building came to be challenged by the eruption of ethnic conflicts. In the political parlance of India today, the very term “North-East” has almost come to denote a region characterized by ethno political movements. One need not make a substantial argument to show that these movements have their origin in the ethno national understanding of the identity. Insurgency, an extreme form of ethno political upsurge, has rocked five of seven States at one time or another, and the remaining two States are highly poised for a similar movement.

Role of Regional Political Parties - After the general election of 1967 there was the emergence and success of many regional parties. In 1967, DMK of Tamil Nadu proved for the first time that a well organized regional party can come to power.¹¹ Ever since the triumph, a trend in India towards the politics of regionalism has been evident.¹² Regional political parties for acquiring power provoke the religious, ethnic or linguistic sentiments of the locals. It has been experienced that such political parties in power often complicate the Centre-State relationship.

Importance of National Integration - India is a vast country with a vast population as its asset. If we get united, this great human force with great resources of the country can carry the whole world with us. Integration is a requirement of every civilized society. It is a comprehensive affair that has various dimensions like political, social, economic, cultural, ethical and psychological. We Indians cannot afford to be parochial, narrow-minded, provincial and communal because we have a great mission to accomplish. Keeping our feet firmly on the ground we should bring about the integration of the Indian people. Political integration has already taken place, but emotional integration is a must for national integration. Toleration, co-operation and feeling of brotherhood should guide us in maintaining the national unity of our country. Let us echo what Pandit Nehru said, “There is no division between North and South, East and West of India. There is only one India of which all us are inheritors, it belongs to all of us.” India has believed in the past and believes today that creativity and change through continuity and a sense of unity amidst diversities is paramount to national integration.

Measures for Achieving National Integration

Political and Cultural Integration - Some people harbour doubts regarding political unity of India. It is true that we have unity in diversity but there has always been a wave which succeeded in binding all the people of this ancient land into one thread. Our places of pilgrimages and holy rivers, instead of being centred at one particular place, are scattered all over the country. For example, look at the Badrinath, Rameshwaram, Kedarnath, Dwaraka Dham and Jagannathpuri. They are situated at the four corners of the country. The Ganga and Yamuna in the north, Godavari in the middle, Krishna and Kaveri in the south, Sindhu in the west, and Brahmaputra in the east are considered as holy and they are worshipped by the entire people of the land. Likewise various cities of the country have been accepted as sacred and also as great cultural centres. This cultural unity has always reminded our people that they are citizens of one land. Therefore we have to strengthen the points of unity and discourage the disruptive forces.

Emotional unity - For national integration, the people of the land must come together into one emotional thread. There can be no national integration unless all the people consider themselves as one. Through emotional integration we get the power and implicit sanction of the people for national integration. At the time of threat to the integrity of the country whole nation has always stood together. When China invaded India in 1962 and Pakistani invasion of 1965 and 1971 on India created the same feeling of anger and anguish. The feeling of oneness is there among Indians It is for the but the need is to strengthen. Through education we have to attract our people towards all these vital points.

Social unity - In the foregoing pages, we have referred to the various types of social inequalities found in our country on the basis of religion, caste, community, class, regions, wealth and poverty. All should be given the idea that everyone's interest lies in the national interest therefore no community should try to strengthen itself at the cost of national interest. We shall have to forget our loyalties to our religion, caste, region, class and community for the sake of social unity. There must not be sectarianism and regionalism. We must always remember that the nation should come first and anything else afterwards.

Inter-Caste and Inter-Provincial Marriages - Some people advocate inter-caste and inter-provincial marriages for obtaining national integration. But what is really meant by inter-caste and inter-provincial marriages that it should not be only welcome but should also be encouraged if the concerned two partners themselves offer for the same. If this practice becomes prevalent, without any pressure from any side, it will definitely strengthen the bond of national integration in due course.

Economic Unity - As we have already discussed about the economic inequality existing in our country. For the sake of national integration we have to see that no part of the country is particularly backward from the economic viewpoint. For this the backward classes and the minority people should be accorded special assistance for their general uplift. In government services and in distributing economic assistance these people should be given special preferences. Our central government and state governments are already taking suitable measures in this sphere.

The National Language - The issue of national language has become very vital for our national integration. According to the Constitution Hindi in the Devnagari Script has been accepted as the national language and this decision was to be implemented by 1965. We shall have to continue our efforts for the development of Hindi in order that in future on some day the entire nation accepts Hindi as a national language. The people of Hindi states must never evince any hurry and restlessness for Hindi, only then the automatic acceptance of Hindi as a national language may be helpful for national integration.

Education - Education is a very powerful weapon for national integration. Through education we may give the necessary motivations to children, i.e., the future citizens of the nation. In the organization of curriculum, in admission in various educational centers and in appointment of teachers our general policy should be such as to encourage the propagation of national elements and not to give any place to caste, religion, class and community. It is true that education should be organized according to local needs, but even in such an organization national elements must never be overlooked.

Non-Government Organizations - Besides the governmental steps, non-government social service organisations can play an important role in strengthening the process of national integration. These organizations can create necessary social awareness for bringing social reforms and change in the mind set of the people. Emergence of awareness can subsequently promote national integration.

Promotion of Secularism - The spirit of secularism is highly necessary in Indian multi-religious society. No political party should indulge in any activity aggravating the differences or causing any tension between various castes, communities or linguistic groups. There is a demand to ban all communal parties and communal organisations by which the danger of communalism can be made less serious. Any sorts of activities creating communal reactions in the public mind should be prohibited. No discrimination among the people on the grounds of religion should be made.

Implementing Uniform Civil Code - The implementation of Uniform Civil Code will make India truly a modern secular state, help eliminate Muslim and Christian 'vote bank' politics, reduce the burden on legal system, and most importantly it will free Muslim women from the archaic, unjust and suppressive practices like triple talaq and male polygamy. In fact, Goa can show the way. It has a Common Family Law which is also called Goa Civil Code and governs all Goans, although it allows some exceptions to some communities. It is certainly not a true Uniform Civil Code, but shows that it is possible to move towards a UCC, despite the bickering of appeasement politicians and vehement opposition of Muslim Mullahs.

CONCLUSION

National integration is highly necessary for modernization. It involves readjustment of loyalties of the people to develop an egalitarian society. It is a process to establish new national identity. As India is a land of unity in diversity, integration is not the process of conversion of diversities uniformly but a congruence of diversities leading to a higher level of unity in which both varieties and uniformities are maintained. Toleration, co-operation and feeling of brotherhood should guide us in maintaining the national unity of our country

. Let us echo what Pandit Nehru said, "There is no division between North and South, East and West of India. There is only one India of which all us are inheritors, it belongs to all of us."

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